

Synthesis and characteristics of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of Schiff base ligands containing triphenylphosphine

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Abstract : The reactions of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes, [MCl₂(PPh₃)₂] (M = Ni or Co) with bidentate Schiff base ligands derived from acetylacetone or benzoylacetone with aniline, *o*-, *m*-nitroaniline have been carried out. The complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, spectral (IR, electronic) and cyclic voltammetric studies and are formulated as [MCl(PPh₃)(L)] (M = Ni or Co; L = bidentate Schiff base ligand). A square planar structure has been tentatively proposed for all the new complexes.

Keywords : Metal complexes of Schiff base ligands, spectral studies, square planar, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

Metal complexes of Schiff base ligands are being continuously studied not only because of their interesting structural and bonding modes but also due to their versatile industrial applications¹. Triphenylphosphine and triphenylarsine complexes of transition metals have been used as catalyst in many industrially important reactions such as hydrogenation, hydroformylation, oxidation, carbonylation, decarbonylation, isomerisation, reduction and alkylation².

We report here the simple procedure for the synthesis of new nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of Schiff base ligands containing triphenylphosphine as additional ligands.

Results and discussion

Stable complexes of general formula [MCl(PPh₃)(L)] (M = Ni or Co; L = bidentate Schiff base ligand) have been obtained. Elemental analysis data are given in Table 1. The characteristic IR frequencies for all the complexes are listed in Table 2. The free Schiff bases show a very strong absorption at 1628 cm⁻¹ which is characteristic of $\nu_{C=O}$. This band is shifted to a lower wave number in the spectra of complexes, and appeared in the region 1625–1618 cm⁻¹, indicating the coordination of Schiff bases through the oxygen atom of C=O group³. The absorption due to $\nu_{C=N}$ of the free ligands appeared in the region 1569–1565 cm⁻¹. In complexes, this band shifts to lower frequency and appears at 1523–

1538 cm⁻¹, indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the metal⁴. In addition, the bands due to triphenylphosphine were also present in the expected region.

The electronic spectra of all the complexes in chloroform showed four bands around 390–256 nm region except the complex [NiCl(PPh₃)(bzac-*m*-nani)]. The spectral data are given in Table 2. Three bands appeared from 256–335 nm region were assigned to intra ligand transition. One band appeared from 360–390 nm region were assigned to LMCT_{s→d} transition. The other peak appeared in the complex [NiCl(PPh₃)(bzac-*m*-nani)] at 420 nm was due to forbidden d-d transition. The peaks were in good agreement with the assignments made earlier for similar other square planar Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes⁵.

Cyclic voltammetric studies were performed for all the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes in acetonitrile solution at a glassy carbon working electrode at scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹. The supporting electrolyte used was 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate ([Bu₄N]ClO₄) in acetonitrile solution. The cyclic voltammogram data are given in Table 3. The redox potentials of the complexes were characterized by well defined waves with E_f values in the range +1.15 to +1.30 V (M^{III}-M^{II}) and -0.74 to -1.16 V (M^{II}-M^I) vs Ag/AgCl electrode. The redox process observed for these complexes are metal centered only⁶. The complex [NiCl(PPh₃)(bzac-ani)] showed reversible redox couples with peak to peak separation value (ΔE_p)

Table 1. Analytical data of the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} Schiff base complexes

Complexes	Yield (%)	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)		
				C	H	N
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(bzac-ani)]	61	Green	53	68.89 (68.31)	4.93 (4.52)	2.60 (2.01)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>o</i> -nani)]	68	Yellow	102	64.03 (64.23)	4.42 (4.38)	4.39 (4.32)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	72	Brown	105	64.03 (64.24)	4.42 (4.37)	4.39 (4.35)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>o</i> -nani)]	68	Brown	132	60.50 (60.20)	4.55 (4.21)	4.86 (4.42)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	65	Yellow	50	59.36 (59.03)	4.46 (4.54)	4.77 (4.65)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(bzac-ani)]	72	Blue	90	68.87 (68.80)	4.92 (4.78)	2.36 (2.33)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>o</i> -nani)]	69	Green	95	64.01 (64.08)	4.42 (4.38)	4.39 (4.40)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	74	Green	102	64.01 (64.09)	4.42 (4.48)	4.39 (4.40)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>o</i> -nani)]	63	Green	65	60.48 (60.32)	4.55 (4.36)	4.86 (4.69)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	76	Blue	105	62.10 (61.93)	4.67 (4.53)	4.99 (5.02)

Table 2. IR absorption frequencies (cm⁻¹) and electronic spectroscopic data (nm) of free ligands and their Ni^{II} and Co^{II} Schiff base complexes

Compd.	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{C=O}$	λ_{max} (ϵ) (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
bzac-ani	1569	1628	-
bzac- <i>o</i> -nani	1569	1628	-
bzac- <i>m</i> -nani	1569	1628	-
acac- <i>o</i> -nani	1565	1628	-
acac- <i>m</i> -nani	1565	1628	-
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(bzac-ani)]	1524	1618	256 (37512), 300 (30341), 332 (26854), 382 (15941)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>o</i> -nani)]	1535	1625	270 (35283), 302 (29813), 334 (26114), 360 (18926)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	1532	1625	280 (33794), 300 (30341), 326 (28329), 374 (16853), 420 (2753)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>o</i> -nani)]	1538	1625	272 (34986), 305 (29163), 334 (26117), 360 (18926)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	1523	1625	280 (33794), 296 (31627), 334 (26117), 390 (14796)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(bzac-ani)]	1524	1618	250 (38749), 305 (29163), 332 (26854), 366 (17467)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>o</i> -nani)]	1535	1625	272 (34986), 303 (29642), 332 (26854), 360 (18926)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	1524	1618	275 (34182), 305 (29163), 335 (25810), 360 (18926)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>o</i> -nani)]	1538	1625	274 (34467), 304 (29439), 334 (26117), 360 (18926)
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	1524	1625	275 (34182), 305 (29163), 335 (25810), 360 (18926)

60 mV, characteristic of a single-step one-electron transfer process⁷. Both the [NiCl(PPh₃)(acac-*m*-nani)] and [CoCl(acac-*m*-nani)] exhibited quasi-reversible oxidation and reduction. The complex [NiCl(PPh₃)(bzac-*m*-nani)]

showed quasi-reversible reduction only. Similarly the complex [CoCl(PPh₃)(bzac-*m*-nani)] showed quasi-reversible oxidation and irreversible reduction. The reason for the irreversibility may be due to short-lived reduced

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric data of the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} Schiff base complexes

Complex	M ^{III} -M ^{II}				M ^{II} -M ^I			
	E_{pa} (V)	E_{pc} (V)	E_f (V)	ΔE_p (mV)	E_{pa} (V)	E_{pc} (V)	E_f (V)	ΔE_p (mV)
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(bzac-ani)]	1.18	1.12	1.15	60	-0.77	-0.71	-0.74	60
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(bzac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	-	-	-	-	-1.18	-1.08	-1.13	100
[NiCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	1.34	1.28	1.31	60	-1.21	-1.05	-1.13	160
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(bzac-ani)]	1.42	1.28	1.35	140	-0.88	-	-	-
[CoCl(PPh ₃)(acac- <i>m</i> -nani)]	1.34	1.26	1.30	80	-1.24	-1.08	-1.16	160

Working electrode : Glassy carbon electrode; Reference electrode : Ag/AgCl electrode ; Supporting electrolyte : [NBu₄]ClO₄ (0.05 M); Solvent : CH₃CN; Concentration of the complex : 0.001 M; Scan rate : 100 mV s⁻¹; $E_f = 0.5 (E_{pa} + E_{pc})$, where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic potentials respectively.

state of the metal ion or due to oxidative degradation of the ligands⁸. The quasi-reversible waves with large peak-to-peak separation value (ΔE_p) are attributed to slow electron-transfer and adsorption of the complexes on the electrode surface⁹.

On the basis of experimental observations, following structure has been tentatively proposed for all the complexes.

M = Ni (or) Co; R = C₆H₅ (or) CH₃; X = C₆H₅, 2-NO₂C₆H₄, 3-NO₂C₆H₄

Experimental

All the reagents used were of analar or chemically pure grade. Solvents were purified and dried according to standard procedures. Elemental analyses were performed at CDRI, Lucknow, India; IR spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr pellets with Nicolet FT-IR spectrophotometer in the 500–4000 cm⁻¹ range. Electronic spectra of the complexes have been recorded in chloroform using a Systronics 119 spectrophotometer in the 200–800 nm range. Cyclic voltammetric studies were carried out with a CHI 604 B electrochemical analyzer in acetonitrile solution. Melting points were recorded with a Technico micro heating table and are uncorrected.

The starting complexes [MCl₂(PPh₃)₂] (M = Ni or Co) and the Schiff base ligands were prepared according to published procedure^{10,11}. The general structure

of the Schiff base ligands used in this study is given below.

R = C₆H₅, CH₃; X = C₆H₅, 2-NO₂C₆H₄, 3-NO₂C₆H₄

Synthesis of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes :

A solution of [MCl₂(PPh₃)₂] (M = Ni or Co) (0.1 g, 0.1 mmol) in ethanol (20 cm³), and the appropriate Schiff bases (0.033–0.043 g, 0.1 mmol) were added in a 1 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was heated under reflux on a water bath for 2 h. The resulting solution was concentrated to 3 cm³ and cooled at 0°C. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*.

References

1. D. Coucouvains, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **26**, 301.
2. R. Karvembu and K. Natarajan, *Polyhedron*, 2002, **21**, 219, 1721.
3. K. P. Balasubramanian, R. Karvembu, V. Chinnusamy and K. Natarajan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2005, **44**, 2450.
4. V. Mahalingam, R. Karvembu, V. Chinnusamy and K. Natarajan, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2006, **64**, 886.
5. M. B. Ferrari, S. Capacchi, F. Bisceglie, G. Pelosi and P. Tarasconi, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2001, **312**, 81; J. Garcia-Tojal, J. L. Pizarro, A. Garcia-Orad, A. R. Perez-Sanz, M. Ugalde, A. A. Diaz, J. L. Serra, M. I. Arriortua and T. Rojo, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2001, **627**, 86.
6. D. Suganya, R. Prabhakaran and K. Natarajan, *Polyhedron*, 2006, **25**, 2223.
7. Z. Shirin and R. N. Mukherjee, *Polyhedron*, 1992, **11**,

- 2625; A. Shyamala and A. R. Chakravarty, *Polyhedron*, 1993, **12**, 1545; F. A. El-Saied, R. M. El-Bahrasawy, M. B. Azzem and A. K. El-Sawaf, *Polyhedron*, 1993, **13**, 1781.
8. A. M. Bond, R. Colton and D. R. Mann, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 4665; A. Basn, T. G. Kasar and N. Y. Sapre, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 4539.
9. A. W. Wallace, W. R. Murphy and J. D. Petersen, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1989, **166**, 47.
10. J. McCarthy, R. J. Hovory, K. Veno and A. E. Martell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5820.
11. G. Nageswara Rao, C. H. Janardhana, K. Pasupathy and P. Mahesh Kumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2000, **39**, 151.